

POLITICAL SCIENCES

AUTHORITARIAN LOGIC AND HYBRID WARFARE: UNDERSTANDING SERBIA'S APPROACH TO KOSOVA

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Abstract

This paper examines the impact of authoritarianism on the dynamics of hybrid warfare in the context of Serbia's policy towards Kosova. Using a research approach that draws on this theme, the paper explores how the logic of authoritarianism undermines the foundations of the liberal order, as evidenced by the political reality of countries like Hungary. In addition, traditional authoritarian states like Serbia have embraced hybrid warfare as a continuation of special warfare against neighboring states, leading to new elements of hybrid warfare that pose a major threat to Kosova.

The primary objective of this essay is to provide a nuanced analysis of the authoritarian logic of Serbian chauvinism towards Albanians. The paper specifically examines the rejection of complexity and the claim of an inversion of historical reality. It also delves into the mindset of the Serbian elite and their farcical logic for territorial expansion. Furthermore, the essay highlights the influence of media and social networks in shaping the dynamics of extreme groups seeking to engage in hybrid activities against Kosova. These dynamics have led to the dehumanization of the school system in Serbia with regards to the Albanians.

Through a comprehensive analysis of the impact of authoritarianism on the logic of hybrid warfare, the paper makes a crucial contribution to understanding contemporary conflict dynamics and the role of non-traditional forms of warfare in shaping state behavior. The paper's findings have important implications for the wider debate on authoritarianism and hybrid warfare, suggesting the need for further research in this area. This paper aims to contribute to the development of more effective strategies to counter the authoritarian logic of hybrid warfare and to promote a more stable and peaceful international order.

Keywords: Authoritarianism, Hybrid warfare, Kosova-Serbia relations, Non-traditional forms of warfare, Media influence.

Introduction

Serbian authoritarianism can be defined as a political system characterized by the concentration of power in the hands of a single leader or group, which uses various forms of coercion and repression to maintain control over the state and society (Petrović, 2014). This type of political system is often associated with suppression of political opposition, limited civil liberties, and the use of force to maintain power.

Throughout the 19th and 20th centuries, and even today, Albanians have been viewed as the "main enemy" of Serbia in Serbian doctrines on security and national interests. This belief, or prejudice, has been embedded in the consciousness of eight to nine generations of Serbs, leading to a complex of self-underestimation and inferiority. This is due, in part, to the fact that Albanians were the first to accept Roman Catholic Christianity among the peoples of Europe and are proud of their history and status as autochthonous people in the region (Thaçi, 2016; Garton Ash, 2017).

Since 1945, democracy has faced its deepest crisis, with a triple crisis in our de facto society: economic (with emphasis on energy), ecological, and political. This raises the question of whether the established political level and governing format in modern Western society can provide hope for the future of democracy, especially given the global shock suffered by the capitalist order in the first two decades of the 21st century. While there are more democratic countries on a planetary level than ever before, counter-revolutions with an

anti-liberal character are appearing on all sides (Levitsky & Ziblatt, 2018; Menasse, 2019). This phenomenon is of deep concern to American political scientists Steven Levitsky and Daniel Ziblatt, who warn that democracy is in danger on the world level, even in places where it was once considered self-evident.

In light of these concerns, Austrian writer Robert Menasse cautions that if we do not emerge from this crisis, which threatens the development of democracy, we will be left with ruins. The threat of hybrid war, or the deepening of the crisis of democracy, has become a real threat to democratic societies and a political challenge (Redžepi, 2022). Serbia's hybrid war against Kosova, combined with geopolitical positioning, is undermining the ability of the EU and Western democracies to make historic decisions. Serbia's permanent hybrid threats to the new democracy in the Republic of Kosova have created a significant dose of fear and anxiety among the population of the Serbian minority in the north of Kosova, who are also under pressure for obedience and submission to Belgrade's power in Kosova. This threat of the nature of hybrid war has also affected other layers of Kosovar society, extending its influence to the judicial and legislative system (Vlahović, 2022).

The session of the Serbian Assembly on February 2, 2023, where the president of Serbia and opposition politicians spoke, demonstrated that Serbian political parties, with few exceptions, as well as populist politicians who dominate the Serbian Parliament, are pushing against liberal democratic norms and values. They

also do not hide their hatred towards the Albanian people. For example, the Serbian president blamed the opposition for releasing the current Prime Minister of Kosovo, Albin Kurti, and 1,600 other hostages from prison in 2001, when he was in power.

These dominant forces in the Serbian political scene have turned into vectors of foreign intervention (Vlahović, 2022).

This essay will shed light on the interaction between the logic of the Serbian mentality, the Serbian Church as an instrument of political power, and authoritarianism in the political sphere. These are powerful weapons in the development of the hybrid war against Kosovo.

Research question: What is the impact of authoritarianism on the dynamics of hybrid warfare in the context of Serbia's policy towards Kosovo?

Hypothesis: The logic of authoritarianism undermines the foundations of the liberal order and contributes to the adoption of hybrid war as a continuation of special war against neighboring states. This results in new elements of hybrid war that present a real threat to Kosovo.

Dependent variable: Instability in the Western Balkans resulting from Serbia's policy towards Kosovo, which is influenced by authoritarianism and hybrid warfare.

Definition of authoritarianism

In the Oxford political dictionary, authoritarianism is defined as "a form of government in which the rulers demand blind obedience from the ruled". The Serbian princes, including the current one - Aleksandar Vučić, not by chance had Frederik the Great as their model. He is quoted as having said that "I have an agreement with my people: they can say what they want and I can do what I want".

In this context, it is aligned with despotism. (Heywood, 2013)

Defining authoritarianism remains a complicated exercise, especially given its normative charge. If "populism embodies and exploits a series of real concerns and demands to improve democratic conditions", authoritarianism itself excludes any form of democracy. If "the essential belief of populism is that a direct representation of the people will bring better governance because it will bypass other forms of decision-making", the belief of authoritarians is quite the opposite. (Mouffe, 2018)

For Rosanvallo (2018), populism is a pathology of democracy, since it exploits the necessarily imperfect nature of electoral representation, authoritarianism does not care at all about democracy and electoral representation.

The term authoritarianism is used in both political science and social psychology. Political scientists explain it as a dictatorial form of rule that, unlike dictatorial totalitarianism, often allows for a certain degree of pluralism. The most important feature of authoritarian forms of government is the absence of underlying ideologies; instead, the bearers of authoritarianism are based on so-called eternal values and traditional cus-

toms. Better than anywhere and anytime, this phenomenon is embodied in the personality of the current Serbian president - Aleksandar Vučić. (Lazić, 2020)

Antonio Scurati (2018), in his historical work on the rise of Italian Fascism, suggested that Benito Mussolini should be considered "an empty man", but able to quickly acquire the skills of a fascist leader who would be able to manipulate the masses of the people to create confidence in the advantages of fascist power.

The current Serbian leader - authoritarian to the core, demonstrates everywhere and whenever a similar, tactical attitude to make his narrative believable to the people. The qualification of the Albanians as the greatest enemy of the Serbian people even today in the age of digitization and the coming artificial intelligence, coincides with the complete premeditated compatibility of the Serbian authoritarian ideology with that of the Italian fascism of the Mussolini era. (Lazić, 2020)

Although, as was said above, authoritarianism remains a fundamentally disputed political concept, in this paper we will try to emphasize the fact that Serbian authoritarianism continues to establish a superior logic over Serbian political thought. As such, Serbian authoritarianism has completely undermined the main frameworks of liberal democracy. (Levitsky & Ziblatt, 2018)

Serbian Democracy and Authoritarianism

A Complex Relationship Serbia has a complex political history, and the contested nature of Serbian authoritarianism has been a subject of interest for many scholars (Vujadinović, 2017). This paper aims to explore the reasons and logic behind the installation of authoritarianism in Serbia, its relationship with democratic practices, and how it led to the genocide in Kosovo at the end of the 20th century. The fight for the definitive disappearance of Albanians from Kosovo was embedded in the logic of Serbian authoritarianism. (Pavković, 2003) The Serbian Army Headquarters' coded document named "Potkovicica (Eng: Horseshoe, Alb: Patkoi)" projected this idea, (Deletant, 1999) which was part of the reason why Serbian authoritarianism mocked the norms of democracy, transforming liberal democracy into a farce of its own kind. (Petrović, 2012) The concept of liberal democracy aims to suppress the authoritarian tendency of ignoring the principle of majority rule. (Gagnon Jr, 2009) In a democratic order, the constituent segments of the political corpus govern in harmony, preventing the abuse of one segment against the organic constituents of society. The essence of political liberalism is best reflected in the main propositions of John Locke (1690), where individual freedom is a structuring social norm and power must be effectively limited and kept in check. Jean-Jacques Rousseau's (1762) concept of individual liberty means that power must be limited and kept in check, with the general will overcoming the expression of public opinion, even a majority. It refers to the type of regime, values, and norms that regulate political and social life for several generations of citizens. The general will, public liberties, and the separation of powers, along with a free press and free speech, prevent tyranny through checks, balances, and oversight. (Bobić & Mitrović, 2018) Did Serbian society develop such over-

sight mechanisms throughout the existence of the modern Serbian state? It is difficult to assert that it managed to do so, even when the Serbian Social Democracy led by Dimitrie Tucović (2013) was laying the foundations of a real democracy in the field of Serbian political thought. Francis Fukuyama (2011) emphasizes that the goal of political liberalism is the management of diversity in pluralistic societies, where power in democracy is limited by the embodiments of the liberal component of democracy. Different sources of power and legitimacy coexist and check each other, arising from the need to regulate public powers for the benefit of individual rights and freedoms. However, did Serbian society ever seriously set these goals and ideals for itself? Since the creation of the state in 1878, Serbia has been promoted as an expansionist state, with its appetite for expansion not hesitating to expand at the right moment even towards western to the detriment of Bosniaks. (Cohen, 1996) The assassination of Prince Franz Ferdinand in 1914 served as the trigger for the start of the First World War, which was based on the prerogatives of the Serbian strategy for the creation of Greater Serbia. (Dedijer, 1990) Political liberalism is based on tolerance and political compromise, while the logic of Serbian authoritarianism is based on the ideology of the Serbian Church and the pre-political ideas of the era of the Serbian Renaissance, on the basis of which the paradigm of modern Serbian nationalism was conceived, contradicting liberal thought. (Pavković, 2007) Serbian authoritarianism owes to a series of practices and expectations derived from true, half-true, and slanderous demands from the Church in relation to Albanians. (Ramet, 2006) Serbian authoritarianism turns out to be the product of a group of political beliefs about how power should be exercised within the corpus of the Serbian state, based on the general claim that elites confiscate its power, resources, and agencies, therefore it, that is, the State, is on par with the Church, must be protected by the army and remain in the service of the Serbian.

This is also determined by the Serbian terminology “vozhd”. According to scientific research, the term “Vozhd” has its etymological origin in the Proto-Slavic language “Vodъ” and was historically used to indicate a chief of a tribe. With the emergence of statehood, the term was also used to refer to a leader or supreme commander, especially when these two roles were combined in one person. This usage was widespread throughout the Slavic regions. (Bjelajac, 2018; Bjelic and Savic, 2004; Milivojevic, 2007)

In the context of Serbian political history, the positions of political leader and supreme commander have always been merged into one person, with the term “Vozhd” being used to refer to this figure. However, this political system has evolved over time into a system characterized by authoritarianism and a constant desire for expansion at the expense of neighboring countries.

One of the consequences of Serbian authoritarianism has been the creation of social homogeneity and resistance to opposing political views, as well as to intellectuals and elites who are perceived as a threat to the Serbian state and identity. Spreading fear and distrust

of politicians and intellectuals is seen as a way to maintain power and control. This feeling continues to be present even today in Serbia. (Bjelajac, 2018; Pavlovic, 2018; Milivojevic, 2007).

Examining the Logic of Neo-Fascism and Its Implications for Society

The rise of neo-fascist leaders around the world has become a concerning trend in recent years. The logic of these leaders, characterized by their authoritarianism and disregard for democratic norms, shares similarities with herd mentality (Gagné, 2020). Modern heads of state and government tend to observe and imitate each other, following the direction of the herd (Stan, 2020). This phenomenon is akin to how Hitler followed Mussolini in the past (Betz & Meret, 2018). In the present, the herd is moving in the direction of fascism, as seen in leaders like Maduro, Erdogan, Putin, Orbán, and Vučić (Albright, 2018, p. 287). Despite their differences, there is much that unites them in their neo-fascist ideology (Wodak & Boukala, 2020).

Neo-fascist rulers treat power not as a privilege, but as an instrument to fulfill their desires (Kallis, 2019). They do not express the need for cooperation with their political opponents, except with oligarchs and specific groups who support them during election campaigns (Gidron & Hall, 2017). They see themselves as “powerful leaders” on whom the fate of the nation depends. This logic of modern neo-fascists is similar to that of despots, as they are willing to reject the complexity of the social order, reject elites, and reject the idea of representation (Ignazi, 2018).

Fascism is characterized as “a redemptive excess of patriotic arbitrariness”, according to Putin’s ideological adoptive father, Ivan Ilyin (Žižek, 2017). Similarly, Vučić’s fascism in relation to the Albanians is based on bloodshed for the extinction of Kosova as a political entity and the annexation of its rich north with mining and water assets at any cost. This logic stems from the neo-colonial concept of the Russian and Serbian elites, who have often enjoyed some kind of support even from a neighborhood of Western European states (Eyal & Buchholz, 2019).

The position of the German minister on the occupation of Ukraine by Russia (Radynski, 2022) highlights the desire of some Western European states to maintain stability and the status quo at all costs, even if this means that Ukraine slips into the territory of Russian neo-colonialism. In this context, the Franco-German draft for Kosova and the conclusion of the imposed dialogue with Serbia represent a tendency for the return of Serbia to regional power and Kosova to a typical neo-colony.

In Article 7 out of a total of 11 articles in the document, which in the meantime was also officially named the Agreement on the normalization path between Kosova and Serbia, it is stated that:

“Both Parties commit to establish specific arrangements and guarantees, in accordance with relevant Council of Europe instruments and by drawing on existing European experiences, to ensure an appropriate level of self-management for the Serbian community in Kosova and ability for service provision in spe-

cific areas, including the possibility for financial support by Serbia and a direct communication channel for the Serbian community to the Government of Kosova. [...]” (European External Action Service, 2023)

Meanwhile, in Article 10, in the second paragraph, it is explicitly emphasized that: “Both Parties confirm their obligation to implement all past Dialogue agreements, which remain valid and binding.” (European External Action Service, 2023)

This paragraph highlights a contentious issue with the 2013 agreement, which is believed to have been influenced by blackmail against the former prime minister of Kosova. The subsequent Agreement on Principles (2015) was considered incompatible with the conditions that the Constitutional Court of Kosova sought to address (*Lidhur Me Vlerësimin E Përputhshmërisë Së Parimeve Që Përmban Dokumenti I Titulluar “Asociacioni/Bashkësia I Komunave Me Shumicë Serbe Në Kosovë [Regarding the Assessment of the Compatibility of the Principles Contained in the Document Entitled “Association/Community of Municipalities With Serbian Majority in Kosova”*, 2015). Furthermore, during the dialogue led by the head of foreign policy of the European Union, Josep Borrell, the Serbian side promoted the “Republika Srbska 2” model in the region, which could result in the defunctionalization of the Republic of Kosova. If implemented, this action could lead to an escalation of hostilities with more catastrophic consequences than the previous conflict of 1998/99, signaling a shift from a hybrid war to a more destructive one.

It has become clear that the Draft Agreement bears a striking resemblance to the 1972 agreement between the Federal Republic of Germany and the German Democratic Republic (German Historical Institute, 1972), which was founded on the principles of Ost-Politik (The Willy Brandt Biography, 1958), a foreign policy initiative developed by Bonn’s political elite, with support from the former chancellor, W. Brandt. The agreement proved successful in the case of the two German states, as the acceptance of political realities led to a new approach by the Federal Republic towards the Soviet Union. The spirit of German-Russian relations, fostered by the inter-German and Ost-Politik agreement, created a tacit understanding between present-day Germany and the Russian Federation regarding a swift Russian invasion of Ukraine, on the assumption that the central government in Kiev would fall quickly. However, this assessment turned out to be wrong, as both the Kremlin and Berlin failed to anticipate the mass resistance of the Ukrainian population.

The Franco-German draft, however, differs from the colonialist logic, but the parties that imposed it could not free themselves from the revisionist concept that has been adopted by a group of Western diplomats in connection with the NATO intervention in Serbia (1999) to put an end to the Serbian genocide. Illustrative of this phenomenon is the statement of Ambassador Christopher Hill, where he expresses his regret for that intervention (Gazeta Tema [Tema Journal], 2023).

Unpredictability as a Weapon: An Analysis of Hybrid Warfare in Kosova

In 1999, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) launched a military intervention in Kosova, then a province of the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, in response to the humanitarian crisis resulting from the conflict between the Yugoslav army and the Kosova Liberation Army (KLA). (BBC News, 1999). The intervention, led by NATO and known as Operation Allied Force, lasted for 78 days and eventually forced Yugoslavia to withdraw its army from Kosova. However, the intervention also had unintended consequences, including strengthening Serbian nationalism and developing a hybrid warfare strategy that Serbia would later use in Kosova and other regions (Bacevich, 2018).

Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova began almost immediately after NATO’s intervention. In response to the deployment of NATO forces in Kosova, Serbian authorities withdrew their military and police forces, leaving a security vacuum. In this vacuum, Serbian paramilitary groups, such as the Akrepi and the Tigers, launched a terror campaign against Albanian civilians, including mass killings, rapes, and forced deportations (Human Rights Watch, 2001).

At the same time, Serbian authorities launched a disinformation campaign aimed at undermining the legitimacy of the Albanian leadership of Kosova and creating confusion among international actors. Serbian media portrayed the KLA as a terrorist organization and accused the Albanian population of committing atrocities against Serbs. Serbian officials also spread rumors and false information about the presence of Al-Qaeda and other terrorist groups in Kosova, in an attempt to convince the international community that Kosova was a security threat (NATO, 2001).

Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova also included cyberattacks and other forms of sabotage. In 2000, Serbian hackers launched a series of attacks against NATO websites, causing significant disruptions (BBC News, 2000). Serbian authorities also engaged in economic warfare, imposing trade and energy blockades in Kosova in an attempt to undermine regional stability (International Crisis Group, 2000).

Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova had several objectives. One was to prevent the creation of an independent Kosova; which Serbia saw as a threat to its territorial integrity and national identity. Another was to create a security threat that would require the presence of international forces in the region, thus limiting Kosova’s independence and sovereignty. Finally, the hybrid war aimed to demonstrate Serbia’s resilience and determination in the face of international pressure and to mobilize popular support for the government (Bacevich, 2018).

Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova was ultimately unsuccessful in achieving its objectives. In 2008, Kosova declared independence from Serbia and is now recognized as a sovereign state by a majority of countries.

However, the lessons of Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova have been studied and applied by other actors, including Russia, which has used similar tactics in Ukraine and elsewhere (Galeotti, 2017). The main lesson of Serbia’s hybrid war in Kosova is that unpredictability can be a powerful weapon in modern warfare. By creating confusion, insecurity, and fear, a state or

non-state actor can undermine the opponent's ability to respond effectively and achieve its objectives at minimal cost and risk. Unfortunately, this also means that the use of hybrid warfare is likely to continue in conflicts around the world, posing a significant challenge to traditional military strategies and international norms. As such, it is essential for policymakers and military leaders to recognize the threat of hybrid warfare and develop effective strategies to counter it, including improved intelligence gathering, stronger cybersecurity measures, and expanded international cooperation. Only by staying ahead of the curve and adapting to the changing nature of modern warfare can we hope to preserve peace and stability in the face of these new and evolving threats.

Conclusions:

In this scientific paper, we have examined the concept of Serbian authoritarianism and its impact on the dynamics of hybrid warfare in the context of Serbia's policy towards Kosovo. We have highlighted the historical tensions between Serbia and Albanians, which have contributed to the development of authoritarianism and the use of hybrid warfare against Kosovo. We have also raised concerns about the threat of hybrid war and the crisis of democracy faced by the Western world.

Our analysis shows that the Serbian government under Aleksandar Vučić embodies many of the key characteristics of authoritarianism, including demands for blind obedience, the absence of underlying ideologies, and a manipulation of the masses through tactical rhetoric. This form of authoritarianism has undermined the foundations of liberal democracy in Serbia and led to a system characterized by authoritarianism and a constant desire for expansion at the expense of neighboring countries.

We have also examined the relationship between Serbian authoritarianism and democracy, highlighting the complex history of these two concepts in Serbia. While liberal democracy aimed to prevent the abuse of power, it is difficult to assert that Serbian society has managed to establish oversight mechanisms to prevent tyranny. The logic of Serbian authoritarianism is based on the ideology of the Serbian Church and the pre-political ideas of the era of the Serbian Renaissance, contradicting liberal thought.

Furthermore, we have discussed the rise of neo-fascist leaders around the world and their rejection of democratic norms, complexity, and elites. The agreement between Kosovo and Serbia may lead to the de-functionalization of the Republic of Kosovo and escalation of hostilities. Therefore, it is essential to monitor and address the rise of neo-fascist leaders and their ideologies to prevent further harm to society.

Finally, we have examined the power of unpredictability as a weapon in modern warfare, demonstrated by Serbia's hybrid war in Kosovo. The continued use of hybrid warfare poses a significant challenge to traditional military strategies and international norms. To counter this threat, policymakers and military leaders must develop effective strategies, including improved intelligence gathering, stronger cybersecurity measures, and expanded international cooperation.

Only through these efforts can we hope to preserve peace and stability in the face of these new and evolving threats.

Based on the conclusions presented in this section of the scientific paper, several strong suggestions can be made:

1. The international community must take a more active role in monitoring and addressing the threat of Serbian authoritarianism and hybrid warfare, particularly in the context of Kosovo. This includes developing more effective strategies for detecting and countering disinformation and propaganda campaigns.

2. It is essential to promote and strengthen the values and principles of liberal democracy in Serbia and other countries facing similar challenges. This can be achieved through support for civil society organizations, independent media, and the rule of law.

3. The rise of neo-fascist leaders and their ideologies must be carefully monitored and addressed, as they pose a significant threat to global peace and stability. This requires a coordinated international response, including efforts to promote tolerance, diversity, and respect for human rights.

4. Policymakers and military leaders must develop effective strategies to counter the threat of hybrid warfare, including improved intelligence gathering, stronger cybersecurity measures, and expanded international cooperation.

5. More research is needed to understand the complex relationship between authoritarianism and democracy in Serbia and other countries facing similar challenges. This includes exploring the historical, cultural, and ideological factors that have contributed to the rise of authoritarianism and the erosion of democratic institutions.

Overall, the scientific paper highlights the urgent need for a coordinated international response to the threat of Serbian authoritarianism, hybrid warfare, and neo-fascism. By working together to promote liberal democratic values, counter disinformation campaigns, and develop effective strategies for modern warfare, we can hope to preserve peace and stability in the face of these evolving threats.

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